

A HYBRID APPROACH TO DATA MANAGEMENT: INTEGRATING JSON DOCUMENTS INTO RELATIONAL DATABASES

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Abstract: *The aim of this paper is to present the theoretical foundation and practical application of the hybrid model using JSON documents in relational databases. The focus is placed on the application of this approach in a Microsoft SQL Server environment, where specific examples illustrate the differences in performance between hybrid, relational and document approaches. A key finding of this paper is the identification of the advantages and challenges associated with the hybrid approach, particularly in terms of query efficiency and modeling flexibility.*

Keywords: *Hybrid database, Relation database, JSON, Data modeling*

1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout the history of software system development, the study of data processing and storage has played a crucial role in the design of software systems. The use of relational databases has represented the standard approach to implementing data storage management. The interpretation of data through tables brought significant innovations to software engineering and enabled easier data management (Codd, 2007).

Despite their widespread use, relational databases exhibit particular drawbacks and structural limitations. The strict schema and table structure in relational databases have proven to be a limitation in systems that require managing flexible data, especially when such data changes dynamically (Kleppmann, 2017).

As a response to these demands, various types of non-relational (NoSQL) databases emerged. The main advantage of these databases is the representation of data using JSON documents (Petković, 2017). The flexible structure of JSON documents has enabled easier data handling, particularly for data with a variable structure.

Relational databases have introduced support for working with JSON documents, thus enabling a new method of data management through a hybrid approach. This approach combines the relational model with JSON documents, allowing the storage of both structured and unstructured data.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Hybrid Approach

Relational databases were originally designed to handle structured data in the form of tables with clearly defined columns and data types. Modern software systems increasingly require processing and storing not only structured but also semi-structured and unstructured data. As a potential architectural solution for such systems, the concept of **Polyglot Persistence** has been developed.

Polyglot persistence is an architectural approach aimed at managing multiple data sources and different types of data storage systems. It involves using various types of databases and technologies within a single system, depending on the nature and requirements of the specific data. For example, relational databases are suitable for transactional data, graph databases can be used for modeling relationships, while document databases are ideal for storing hierarchical data (McMurtry, Oakley, Sharp, Subramanian, & Zhang, 2013). A system designed in this way ensures optimal performance regardless of the volume and variety of data it needs to process.

However, managing and integrating different databases and technologies can be complex and costly. This is where **hybrid databases** come into play, offering a solution that combines relational and non-relational models within the same technology stack.

Microsoft SQL Server, for instance, supports graph database capabilities, enabling data modeling through nodes and edges, which simplifies the representation of relationships between entities. This feature is particularly useful in applications like social networks and recommendation systems.

Additionally, SQL Server supports working with JSON and XML documents, providing a balance between efficiency and system complexity. Importantly, the hybrid approach is implemented within a single technology, eliminating the need for external NoSQL solutions.

With these enhancements, SQL Server has become a powerful tool for implementing hybrid models, enabling the development of systems that meet the requirements of both traditional and modern architectures without leaving the well-established and mature SQL ecosystem.

2.2. JSON Document

The main advantage of non-relational databases is their ability to represent data using the **JSON structure**. JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is a lightweight data-interchange format used to represent structured information in a way that is easy to read and write for humans. The fundamental structure of a JSON document consists of key-value pairs (Pezoa, Reutter, Suárez, Ugarte, & Vrigoč, 2016).

This data format resembles the structure of classes and their attributes in object-oriented programming languages. The flexibility of the JSON schema allows the storage of heterogeneous and unstructured data even within relational databases. Using JSON documents in this way serves as a method of adapting strict data schemas to accommodate more flexible and dynamic data structures.

2.3. JSON in Sql Server

Since SQL Server 2016, Microsoft's database system has introduced significant support for working with JSON documents, making it a competitive option for handling semi-structured and unstructured data. A JSON document is stored as plain text within NVARCHAR or VARCHAR columns, enabling seamless integration with existing relational model structures (Microsoft, 2024).

```
DECLARE @json NVARCHAR(MAX);
SET @json = '{"info": {"address"
                [{"city": "Belgrade"},
                {"city": "Paris"},
                {"city": "Madrid"}]}}';
```

This version introduced numerous functions that facilitate efficient storage and processing of JSON documents (Microsoft, 2024).

- **ISJSON** – the function checks whether the input text is in a valid JSON format.
- **JSON_VALUE** – this function extracts the value of a specified attribute from a JSON document. It takes a path parameter that allows direct access to attribute values.
- **JSON_OBJECT** – this function takes key-value pairs as input and creates a JSON object.
- **JSON_ARRAY** – this function creates a JSON array from the provided values, which may be of different data types.
- **JSON_QUERY** – this function returns an object or array from a JSON text. The difference between JSON_QUERY and JSON_VALUE lies in their return types: JSON_VALUE returns scalar values, while JSON_QUERY returns full JSON objects or arrays.
- **JSON_MODIFY** – This function updates the value of an attribute within a JSON document and returns the updated document. It can also add new attributes or remove existing ones. Moreover, it allows changes within JSON arrays.
- **OPENJSON** – enables tabular representation of a JSON document. Each object becomes a row, while key-value pairs are represented as columns. This function is especially useful when working with structured or semi-structured data, as it allows the use of standard relational operations on JSON.
- **FORJSON** – this clause formats query results as JSON text. It offloads the responsibility of generating JSON from the application layer to the database engine. The clause supports two modes: AUTO for automatic structure and PATH for custom output formatting.

3. PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION

This section of the paper presents the practical implementation of basic operations (SELECT, INSERT, and UPDATE) using three different approaches: relational, hybrid, and document. The experiment uses a domain model with a focus on hierarchical inheritance.

Figure 1: Domain model

In the relational model, the Table per Type (TPT) strategy separates data into related tables to avoid NULLs and represent inheritance. The hybrid model stores parent entities in relational tables and embedding subtypes data as JSON documents. The implementation of the relational and hybrid models was carried out using SQL Server technology. In the document model, each standalone entity is stored as a separate document in MongoDB, simplifying handling of diverse data.

Table 1: Implementaion cross approaches

Relation	Hybrid	Document
<pre> CREATE TABLE Employee (id BIGINT PRIMARY KEY, firstname NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, lastname NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, email NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, birthday DATE NOT NULL, title NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, phone NVARCHAR(50) NOT NULL); CREATE TABLE Developer (id BIGINT PRIMARY KEY FOREIGN KEY REFERENCES employee(id) ON DELETE CASCADE, seniority NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, yearsOfExperience INT NOT NULL, isRemote BIT NOT NULL); CREATE TABLE Manager (id BIGINT PRIMARY KEY FOREIGN KEY REFERENCES employee(id) ON DELETE CASCADE, department NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, realisedProject INT NOT NULL, method NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL); CREATE TABLE SoftwareDeveloper (id BIGINT PRIMARY KEY FOREIGN KEY REFERENCES developer(id) ON DELETE CASCADE, programmingLanguage NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, ide NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, isfullstack BIT NOT NULL); </pre>	<pre> CREATE TABLE Employee (id BIGINT PRIMARY KEY, firstname NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, lastname NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, email NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, birthday DATE NOT NULL, title NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, phone NVARCHAR(50) NOT NULL, manager NVARCHAR(MAX) NULL); CREATE TABLE Developer (id BIGINT PRIMARY KEY FOREIGN KEY REFERENCES employee(id) ON DELETE CASCADE, seniority NVARCHAR(255) NOT NULL, yearsOfExperience INT NOT NULL, isRemote BIT NOT NULL, softwareDeveloper NVARCHAR(MAX) NULL); </pre>	<pre> { "_id": ObjectId("ManagerId"), "firstname": "String", "lastname": "String", "email": "String", "birthday": "Date", "title": "String", "phone": "String", "department": "String", "realisedProject": "Number", "method": "String" } { "_id": ObjectId("SoftwareDeveloperId"), "firstname": "String", "lastname": "String", "email": "String", "birthday": "Date", "title": "String", "phone": "String", "seniority": "String", "yearsOfExperience": "Number", "isRemote": true, "programmingLanguage": "String", "ide": "String", "isFullStack": true } </pre>

In the relational approach, data is inserted into two tables—one for general employee attributes and another for manager-specific details. The hybrid approach uses a single table with general attributes as columns and manager-specific data stored as a JSON document. In the document approach, all data is stored together in a single document.

Table 2: Implementation INSERT query

Approach	Query
Relation	<pre>INSERT INTO Employee (id, firstname, lastname, email, birthday, title, phone) VALUES (@Id, @FirstName, @LastName, @Email, @Birthday, @Title, @Phone); INSERT INTO manager (id, department, realisedproject, method) VALUES (@Id, @Department, @RealisedProject, @Method);</pre>
Hybrid	<pre>INSERT INTO Employee (id, firstname, lastname, email, birthday, title, phone,manager) VALUES (@Id, @FirstName, @LastName, @Email, @Birthday, @Title, @Phone,@Manager);</pre>
Document	<pre>public void InsertManager(ManagerModel manager) { manager.Role = "Manager"; _employeesCollection.InsertOne(manager); }</pre>

The SELECT query retrieves all managers who are younger than thirty years old and use the Agile methodology. The results are sorted by date of birth in ascending order.

Table 3: Implementation SELECT query

Approach	Query
Relation	<pre>SELECT e.id, e.firstname, e.lastname, e.email, e.birthday, e.title, e.phone, m.department, m.realisedProject, m.method FROM Employee e INNER JOIN Manager m ON e.id = m.id WHERE DATEDIFF(YEAR, e.birthday, GETDATE()) < 30 AND m.method = 'Agile' ORDER BY e.birthday ASC;</pre>
Hybrid	<pre>SELECT e.id, e.firstname, e.lastname, e.email, e.birthday, e.title, e.phone, m.department, m.realisedProject, m.method FROM Employee e CROSS APPLY OPENJSON(manager) WITH(Department NVARCHAR(100) '\$.Department', RealisedProject INT '\$.RealisedProject', Method NVARCHAR(20) '\$.Method')AS m WHERE DATEDIFF(YEAR, e.birthday, GETDATE()) < 30 AND m.method = 'Agile' ORDER BY e.birthday ASC;</pre>
Document	<pre>public List<ManagerModel> GetManagersYoungerThan30AndAgileMethodSorted() { var filterForManagers = Builders<ManagerModel>.Filter.And(Builders<ManagerModel>.Filter.Eq("Role", "Manager"), Builders<ManagerModel>.Filter.Gt(m=>m.BirthDay,DateTime.UtcNow.AddYears(-30)), Builders<ManagerModel>.Filter.Eq(m=>m.Method,"Agile")); var foundManagers = ManagersCollection .Find(filterForManagers) .Project<ManagerModel>(ManagerProjection) .ToList(); return foundManagers; }</pre>

This query sets the methodology to Lean for every manager who belongs to the IT or Logistics department and is between forty and fifty years old. In the relational approach, the operation is performed across two tables, while in the hybrid approach, the condition applies to both the table and the embedded document.

Table 4: Implementation UPDATE query

Approach	Query
Relation	<pre>UPDATE Manager SET method = 'Lean' WHERE department IN ('IT','Logistics') AND id IN (SELECT e.id FROM Employee e WHERE DATEDIFF(YEAR, e.birthday, GETDATE()) BETWEEN 40 AND 50);</pre>
Hybrid	<pre>UPDATE Employee SET manager = JSON_MODIFY(manager,'\$.Method','Lean') WHERE JSON_VALUE(manager,'\$.Department') IN ('IT','Logistics') AND DATEDIFF(YEAR, birthday, GETDATE()) BETWEEN 40 AND 50;</pre>
Document	<pre>public void UpdateMethodByYearsAndDepartment() { var filterManager = Builders<ManagerModel>.Filter.And(Builders<ManagerModel>.Filter.In(m => m.Department,new []{ "IT", "Logistics" }), Builders<ManagerModel>.Filter.Gt(m=>m.BirthDay,DateTime.UtcNow.AddYears(-50)), Builders<ManagerModel>.Filter.Lt(m=>m.BirthDay,DateTime.UtcNow.AddYears(-40))); var updateMethod = Builders<ManagerModel>.Update.Set(m => m.Method, "Lean"); ManagersCollection.UpdateMany(filterManager, updateMethod); }</pre>

4. ANALYSIS OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This chapter presents the results of an experimental comparison of three distinct approaches—relational, hybrid, and non-relational—in terms of the execution of fundamental operations: SELECT, INSERT, and UPDATE. Execution time was measured for each operation across varying data volumes (5,000, 50,000, and 500,000 records), using the *BenchmarkDotNet* tool. This benchmarking library, implemented in C#, ensures high-precision and statistically reliable results. All tests were performed under identical hardware conditions, with the following specifications: Intel i7 10750h 2.60GHz processor, 16 GB DDR4 ram memory, and Windows 10 Pro operating system. The execution times are reported in milliseconds.

Figure 2: Insert Operation Performance

The results for the INSERT operation show that the Document approach consistently has the slowest data insertion times. Its execution time is significantly higher compared to the relational and hybrid approaches. The hybrid approach performs best, with the relational approach closely following. This can be attributed to MongoDB’s document handling and limited optimization for bulk inserts, whereas relational databases often leverage batch inserts and transactional management, resulting in faster data insertion.

Figure 3: SELECT Operation Performance

Figure 4: UPDATE Operation Performance

Based on the SELECT query results, the relational approach shows the best performance across all data volumes. Document approach is significantly slower, especially with larger datasets, while the hybrid approach performs moderately but leans closer to the relational model. This is largely due to SQL's efficient indexing and query optimization, unlike MongoDB's document structure, which is less suited for complex queries.

Regarding the UPDATE operation, document model performs the slowest, particularly with larger datasets. The hybrid model is slightly better, while the relational approach is the fastest and most consistent due to its optimized mechanisms for updating specific values, unlike MongoDB which often rewrites entire documents.

5. CONCLUSION

This research demonstrates that relational, non-relational, and hybrid databases each offer distinct advantages and disadvantages depending on query complexity and data structure. The relational model provides stability and efficiency when working with structured data and complex queries, while the document approach allows greater flexibility for dynamic and unstructured data.

The hybrid model, combining features of both systems, proved to be an optimal solution for scenarios requiring fast execution of simple queries and data insertion. However, its performance decreases with more complex operations, especially those involving grouping, sorting, and data updates.

In conclusion, the choice of a suitable database should be guided by the specific needs of the application and the nature of the data. The hybrid approach represents a promising solution that, with further optimization, can significantly contribute to the development of efficient and sustainable software systems.

Future research could investigate the security implications of each approach, focusing on data protection, access control, and compliance with relevant regulations.

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